

The Effect of Education and Job Training on Employee Performance at Pt. Masmindo Dwi Area in Latimojong District, Luwu District

Siti Aviva Rahma¹
Makassar State University,
Faculty of Economics and Bussiness Makassar, Indonesia

Zainal Ruma², Burhanuddin³, Romansyah Sahabuddin⁴,
Uhud Darmawan Natsir⁵
Makassar State University,
Faculty of Economics and Bussiness Makassar, Indonesia

Abstract:- This research aims to analyze the influence of education and job training on employee performance. This research was conducted at PT. Masmindo Dwi Area in Latimojong District, Luwu Regency. Population in this research were all employees of PT. Masmindo Dwi Area in Latimojong District, Luwu Regency, totaling 130 people. Sample In this study there were 57 respondents. This research is research explanatory quantitative.

The results of this research show that education (X1) is partial does not have a significant effect on employee performance (Y) with value significant $0.202 > 0.05$, and the job training variable (X2) partially has a significant influence on employee performance (Y) with value significant $0.001 < 0.05$. Meanwhile, the calculated F results show a value of 11.805 is greater than F table 3.168. This shows education and job training simultaneously has a significant effect on performance employees at PT. Masmindo Dwi Area in Latimojong District, Regency Luwu.

Keywords:- Education, Job Training, Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of science and technology today leads to development and growth in all areas of life, requiring companies to continue to grow and develop to face new, very complex problems. This development is an integral part of government and private organizations. This can be seen in new work methods, more modern work tools, new work requirements, which always demand responsibility and vitality from the organization, which also allows for adaptability. Besides, there are more and more The emergence of new companies with various types of business indicates that business competition is getting stronger. The business world is challenged to face ongoing changes in order to maintain its existence so that it is not easily eroded by dynamic environmental conditions.

Human resources are one component in a company organization. Human resource management plays a role in creating a competent and qualified workforce. In other words, they must participate in all action decisions made by the company. According to Dilip Bhatt quoted by Amir

(2015:93) companies must invest most of their efforts in human resource management by 75 percent, equipment and technology by 10 percent, and planning systems by 15 percent. According to Notoatmodjo in Indrastuty (2019), "An agency must be supported by quality human resources because human resources play a very important role in managing business or activities in the agency." The excellence of a company can be achieved through several factors. One of these factors is the company's internal capabilities, namely human resources quality. From this point of view, human resources are the most important in a company and must be possessed to achieve company goals, because of their role as the subject of implementing policies and operational activities of an organization. Therefore, the human resources that companies currently need are human resources who have high job performance, are able to master technology and are responsive to changes that occur in current technology, must have the same insight, creativity, knowledge and vision as the company.

The higher the education, the higher the performance shown (Usman, 2022). As an employee's education increases, he or she has broader insight or vision, and supported by work experience, the employee has added value in carrying out his or her duties. In general, it can be said that an employee's education can reflect the employee's intellectual skills and abilities. To support employee performance in addition to Education is also needed as well as workforce training. A company provides training or education to employees with the aim of bridging the gap between the factual conditions of employee performance and the ideal standards of performance for the position occupied by the employee as a result of a lack of knowledge, skills and attitudes. certain work. Training is an activity of a company which aims to improve and develop the attitudes, behavior, skills and knowledge of employees in accordance with the wishes of the company concerned (Mangkunegaran, 2009). Each individual's skills must be developed continuously, one of which is by implementing education and training programs.

Employee education and training can improve performance employees both now and in the future from time to time. Job training designed to effectively achieve company goals, maximize profits, and keep the company ahead of the competition. However, before making strategic

decisions about human resource development, a comprehensive analysis needs to be carried out about the influence of education and job training on employee performance in the PT environment. Masmino Dwi Area. This analysis provides a better understanding of the extent to which workplace training and education influences employee performance and whether these programs have produced the intended benefits. Training and education are the same as development, namely a process of improving both technical and managerial skills.

Problems that arise in corporate education and training are often not in accordance with organizational, task and individual needs so that they do not support employee performance and careers, even though the costs incurred are quite high. The education and training that is carried out often does not solve the problem because the company chooses the wrong method. This research will examine the extent to which the education and job training that has been provided to employees contributes to improvement their performance in carrying out their duties and responsibilities in company.

Education and training are two important factors in human resource development in the organization. Education has a big influence in supporting human activities. This can be proven in the workplace, many companies consider the educational background of prospective employees before hiring them for required positions. For companies, higher education provides employees with the opportunity to take the right steps in operations. In a competitive business environment, companies have demands to improve employee performance so that it is meaningful and effective in achieving company goals. Education is an important foundation in employee development. When working, a person must have education that is appropriate to the type of work he takes. Improving the quality of employees can occur if there is education, knowledge and skills so that they can increase performance and productivity employees as economic actors.

PT Masmino Dwi Area is a company operating in the field mining, growth-oriented companies and long-term success, PT. Masmino Dwi Area understands the importance of developing the skills of its employees as a valuable resource. Previously the author had made initial observations to see the conditions at PT. Masmino Dwi Area where the author has carried out an interview process with several employees and based on initial observations there is a condition where there are still many employees whose work placements do not match their field or educational background, but the educational background of employees at PT. Masmino Dwi Different areas are not really a basic benchmark in becoming an employee.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Definition of Human Resource Management

Human resources are an important asset and act as the main driving factor in the implementation of all agency activities or functions, so they must be managed well through Human Resources Management (HRM).

Ajabar (2020) states that human resources are the most important key for an organization to achieve its goals. According to Riniwati (2016:1) people who work within an organization are personnel, workers, employees or employees.

Sudarmanto (2018:22) states that resource management Human Resources is strengthening, developing and maintaining human resources in an organization so that they can make the best contribution to achieving organizational goals based on their skills, insight and abilities.

The main goal of human resource management is to creating a healthy and productive work environment for employees, and develop one's potential so that one can make a contribution maximum for the organization and ensure that human resources used efficiently and effectively to achieve business goals has been established.

B. Definition of Education

Triwiyanto (2014:113), "Education is a conscious and conscious effort planned to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential for national and state life."

Ruky (2021) states that education is an activity employees in an effort to master certain skills, knowledge.

C. Definition of Training

Every company will experience a transition in usage more advanced technology to streamline operational activities to make them more efficient. However, the role of humans is always needed because the role of technology only makes business easier and faster. Efforts that can be made so that employees are able to adapt to these conditions are through implementing training programs.

Mangkuprawira (2014:134) "Training for employees is a process of teaching certain knowledge and skills, as well as attitudes so that employees become more skilled and able to carry out their responsibilities the answer is getting better, according to the standards." Chan in Priansa (2016:175) states that "Training is learning provided in order to improve performance related to current job". Dessler (2010) states that training is the process of giving employees the skills they need.

D. Definition of Performance

Marhawati (2022) states that performance is the quality of work employees as they carry out their work during the period certain time through work processes in accordance with company standards. Employee performance plays an important role in determining the success of the organization in achieving its goals set. Hasibuan (2016:94) states that performance is a result work done by someone based on ability, experience, honesty and time in carrying out assigned tasks to her. Rivai (2015:309) states that performance is behavior real work performance shown by each employee produced according to their role in the company.

Performance is the achievement of organizational goals, which can be achieved manifested in the form of quantitative or qualitative results, creativity, flexibility, reliability, or other goals desired by the organization. Performance emphasis can be short term or long term, including at the individual, group or organizational level. Individual performance contribute to group performance, which in turn influences organizational performance. In highly effective organizations, leadership helps create positive synergies, that is, more overall greater than the sum of its parts. At no other level does it exist one criterion measure that accurately reflects performance.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The type of research used is explanatory research with quantitative, explanatory approach is research that aims analyze the relationship between one variable and another variable or how a variable affects other variables. This research used to explain the relationship between independent variables and variables bound.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. The Influence of Education on Employee Performance at PT. Masmino Dwi Area in Latimojong District, Luwu Regency.

This research took 57 samples from the questionnaires distributed. The results of this research indicate that the Education variable (X1) does not have a significant influence on employee performance at PT. Masmino Dwi Area in Latimojong sub-district, Luwu Regency. This could be because there are still many employees whose field of work does not match their educational background. This result may be surprising given the common view that education is an important factor in improving performance. Education is only one of many factors that influence employee performance, and its results non-significant can be explained by the dominance of other factors.

Based on the explanation above, it shows that there may be other factors such as work experience, training, motivation, support management, work environment and other more psychological factors important in influencing employee performance at PT. Masmino Dwi Area in Latimojong District, Luwu Regency. However, education remains an important element to consider in improving

employee performance.

B. The Effect of Job Training on Employee Performance at PT. Masmino Dwi Area in Latimojong District, Luwu Regency.

The results of this research indicate that the job training variable (X2) has a significant influence on employee performance at PT. Masmino Dwi Area in Latimojong sub-district, Luwu Regency.

Job training programs include a wide range of training provide sustainable benefits. This research shows that Job training has a positive and significant effect on performance employees of PT Masmino Dwi Area. Therefore, the company must continue invest in effective and relevant training programs for ensure that employees remain competent, engaged and capable face constant changes in the business world.

C. The Effect of Education and Job Training on Performance Employees at PT. Masmino Dwi Area in the District Latimojong, Luwu Regency.

The results of this research show that education and training Simultaneous work has a significant influence on employee performance. It can be concluded that education and job training both play an important role in improving employee performance at PT. Masmino Dwi Area in Latimojong District, Luwu Regency.

Education and training complement each other in improving employee performance. Effective training can improve skills and employee knowledge, this can increase productivity and work quality. Education also provides benefits, employees who continually learn and develop themselves have better opportunities to develop and contribute more to the company, so that education and training will improve employee performance.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of research conducted at PT. Masmino Dwi Area in Latimojong District, Luwu Regency, the conclusions that can be drawn taken are as follows:

- The Education variable (X1) partially has no influence significant impact on employee performance at PT. Masmino Dwi Area in Latimojong District, Luwu Regency, in other words, H0 is rejected. This could be because there are still many employees in the field his work does not match his educational background. Education is only one of many influencing factors employee performance, and insignificant results can be explained by the dominance of other factors that are more important in influencing employee performance at PT. Masmino Dwi Area in the District Latimojong, Luwu Regency.
- The Job Training variable (X2) partially has a significant effect on employee performance at PT. Masmino Dwi Area in the District Latimojong Luwu Regency, in other words H1 is accepted. This matter because job training

programs cover a wide range training that provides ongoing benefits for improvement employee performance. Variables Education (X1) and Job Training (X2) simultaneously has a significant effect on employee performance at PT. Masmindo Dwi Area in Latimojong District, Luwu Regency, in other words H2 is accepted. Education and training complement each other deeply improve employee performance, so it can be concluded that education and training both play an important role in improve employee performance at PT. Masmindo Dwi Area in Latimojong District, Luwu Regency.

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